

International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA)

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<https://aircse.org/journal/ijnsa.html>

SCOPE OF THE JOURNAL

The **International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA)** is a bi monthly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the computer Network Security & its applications. The journal focuses on all technical and practical aspects of security and its applications for wired and wireless networks. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Modern security threats and countermeasures, and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Topics of Interest

- Network and Wireless Network Security
- Mobile, Ad Hoc and Sensor Network Security
- Peer-to-Peer Network Security
- Database and System Security
- Intrusion Detection and Prevention
- Internet Security & Applications
- Security & Network Management
- E-mail security, Spam, Phishing, E-mail fraud
- Virus, worms, Trojon Protection
- Security threats & countermeasures (DDoS, MiM, Session Hijacking, Replay attack etc.)
- Ubiquitous Computing Security
- Web 2.0 security
- Cryptographic protocols
- Performance Evaluations of Protocols & Security Application

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2. Accept with minor changes
3. Weak Accept with major changes
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Total Cites	121				
Impact Factor	0.139				
Discipline Impact	Discipline	WJCI	Rank	Quartile	WJCI Percentile
	Data Security and Computer Security	0.465	29/36	Q4	19.44
	Computer Network	0.304	58/73	Q4	20.55
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Total Cites	148				
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Discipline Impact	Discipline	WJCI	Rank	Quartile	WJCI Percentile
	Data Security and Computer Security	0.349	29/35	Q4	17.14
	Computer Network	0.299	69/77	Q4	10.39
	Average Value	0.324	—	—	13.77

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